

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC MOBILITY IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Today, the essence of the process of academic mobility has become the subject of study by a wide range of scientists in the world. The authors analyze the semantic content of such phenomena as: academic and social mobility of a future specialist in connection with obtaining higher professional education. The article substantiates the relationship between educational quality and academic mobility. Today it is celebrated as an inevitable phenomenon dictated by global integration processes. After all, the world increasingly values correct constructive communications and the ability to build dialogic and partnership relationships.

Keywords: mobility, students, structure, development, academic environment

Introduction

A new look at global changes in society has brought to life the need to modernize education, construct a new educational environment, and professional education, which focuses on the development of foreign language competence and academic mobility in accordance with the value priorities of the individual.

One of the important problems of the modern process of modernization of the educational process of a university is the development of academic mobility of both students and teaching staff. The development of academic mobility of students in higher professional educational institutions is one of the highest priority areas in educational policy.

The structure of academic mobility assumes the unity and interconnection of the following aspects:

- implementation of professional knowledge and skills that meet international standards;
- the readiness of future specialists to perceive international technological innovations;
- expanding the profile of professional training of specialists;
- freedom and variability in choosing an educational route, educational modules and educational institutions;
- development of creativity and critical thinking of the individual;
- readiness of future specialists to actively use a foreign language.

The development of academic mobility of university students is implemented on the basis of the principles of continuity, variability, freedom of choice, framework implementation of the variable part of the main educational program (50% and 70% for undergraduate and graduate programs), pragmatism, and subjectivity.

Literature review

The concept of "academic mobility" was included in the pedagogical thesaurus in connection with the transition of the higher education system to a multi-level system of training specialists. From the perspective of the development of the international educational

space, academic mobility is aimed at optimizing international relations in the implementation of educational programs, student exchange and joint activities of teaching staff.

Academic mobility is consistent with the training of students in foreign universities, as well as the activities of teachers and staff in foreign educational or scientific institutions, which in pedagogical theory is interpreted as external (international) mobility.

Academic and other types of mobility cannot be reduced to specific actions, technologies and mechanisms associated only with the student exchange system of educational institutions. This is a rather complex and multifaceted process of management at a new stage of international cooperation on the exchange of training programs, the introduction into the educational process of universities of a multi-level system for training specialists of the new generation.

The formation of a modern organizational culture, consistent with the research activities of students, as a creative process of acquiring new knowledge and the meaning of the holistic life activity of the subject; means and methods of improving the quality of the educational process of a university is one of the ways to form individual and social mobility among students.

Methods

In order to determine the pedagogical conditions for the development of academic mobility of university students, informational conversations and surveys were organized and conducted. The respondents were students and employers. The content of the survey questions included students' opinions on the positive and negative aspects of mobile education, planning internships, and obtaining additional professional education at foreign universities.

The results of the survey made it possible to establish that 67% of students studying under the double degree system independently decided to study along this educational path.

It should be noted that 6% of students who have completed training under the double degree system plan to stay and work in their hometown, 25% intend to work in the metropolitan areas of their home state, and 69% of students plan to organize employment in other

countries, for example in Korea, the United States of America, Germany.

A significant issue is the lack of interest in organizing mobile education and the introduction of a credit-modular system at a university represented by enterprises, institutions, and organizations acting as an employer as a consumer in the labor market of young specialists.

Study participants strongly believe that experience in international academic interaction provides graduates with the ability to work in an intercultural, global professional environment. A double diploma allows you to recognize and understand systems of linguistic, political, and practical phenomena, which ensures the formation of professional, general cultural and social competencies, and helps in establishing interpersonal relationships.

The data obtained from a survey of potential employers is interesting. Almost all the qualities and characteristics of future potential employees that students develop during their stay abroad are rated by employers as relatively important. These include: the ability to cooperate, reliability and responsibility, the ability to effectively solve problems, adaptability and the ability to respond to changes in the external environment. At the same time, respondents note the importance of such qualities as the ability to interact with people from a different culture, knowledge of the traditions of foreign countries and cultures, and readiness to work abroad. Любопытно, что энтузиазм и амбиции в работе по степени важности оказались в середине списка значимых показателей. Tolerance, analytical thinking, empathy, and the ability to work in a team turned out to be the last in importance for employers. At the same time, all employers agree that the experience of participating in academic mobility contributes to the development of professional and general cultural competencies, as well as the personal growth of a future specialist.

Results

In the process of developing a student's readiness for academic mobility as a personal quality in a future professional, a special role belongs to the development of innovative technologies of the educational process, which is based on the creation of a system of subject-subject relations between its participants. An important role belongs to identifying the conditions for the comprehensive development of students, including practical testing of strengths and abilities in various types of activities: educational, professional, project.

To identify the characteristics of students moving for training, internships, etc., we conducted an Internet survey of students who were abroad: internships in production (industrial practice), educational programs abroad, study, work, etc. The survey showed that 97% of students received significant influence on their own worldview (consciousness). This is explained by the fact that they lived in a foreign country without parental care, worked in a foreign language environment and earned money on their own. The thesis is confirmed that among the values of young people, family occupies the highest position. Participants also point to an expansion of thinking: seemingly familiar concepts such as

discipline, prudence, and responsibility are perceived in a new way. Traveling to a foreign country teaches you to appreciate your native spaces in a new way. Opportunities arise to re-set your own priorities, which strengthens your character.

83% of respondents indicated that the level of acquired knowledge in a foreign language was insufficient; there was a lack of vocabulary, knowledge of grammar, and sociocultural characteristics of the recipient country.

53% of those who studied abroad noted that the difference between the curricula of Uzbekistan and foreign countries is significantly different. The same applies to the organization of the educational process. For example, writing and defending theses takes place only under the guidance of a supervisor and is highly specialized. Typically, such work is performed on behalf of an enterprise or company. That is, scientists and students work on a specific project and then implement it into production. The educational process is organized in such a way that most of the time students work independently (2-3 days a week independent work, other days with teachers).

92% indicated a high level of technological support for the educational process, when all information about teachers, schedules, workloads, etc. can be found on the university website. Also, each teacher has his own blog, where he communicates with students. Computerization, in a certain way, also helps students in learning and searching for information. For example, the university installs special programs on student laptops to translate terms. This obviously makes it easier to work with textbooks. Students note that the use of the latest technologies in classes makes them interesting and meaningful.

The productive direction of the development of academic mobility of university students should contribute to personal self-affirmation, self-realization in the course of solving educational problems in the conditions of an attitude towards success and the desire for success.

The study identified the difficulties that arose among students who took part in international educational exchange programs while staying and studying in another country. This allows us to identify the causes of these difficulties and assist students in eliminating these causes in the process of formation and development of their academic mobility.

Analysis of the results shows that most of the difficulties encountered by students who took part in international exchange educational programs are related to the integration of students into a different cultural environment. The number of such subjects amounted to 38.2% of the total number of respondents. A significant number (21.8%) of difficulties are associated with the insufficient level of foreign language proficiency of students, as a result of which there is a decrease in communication capabilities. A lower percentage reflects the difficulties of integrating students into the educational or educational and professional environment of the host country. It was revealed that about 10% of students experience difficulties in achieving educational or educational and professional goals in their own subject area.

18.1% of respondents participating in the experiment did not experience serious difficulties when participating in international exchange educational programs.

Conclusions

Academic mobility is one of the priority areas of international education, and the main pedagogical condition for its development is the process of inclusive learning for students. The main structural components of the pedagogical process are the following: establishing equal partnerships between the university and foreign educational institutions; implementation of the opportunity for students to test themselves in another system of organizing higher professional education; students obtaining additional knowledge in related fields.

These components are the conditions for a student to receive a double diploma. Through academic mobility, the student's internal need is realized, providing the student with integration into the production sphere through the space of relationships and interconnections.

So, academic mobility is, first of all, an opportunity for students, provided by partner universities, to form and improve their professional educational preparation through the choice of subjects, disciplines, courses, educational institutions in accordance with their inclinations and aspirations.

Academic mobility gives each student the opportunity to build his own educational trajectory within the framework of the functioning of the system of higher professional education in general and the system of

continuing education in particular. In order to build and implement an international educational trajectory, the future specialist needs to form and develop international educational competencies, and the university needs to ensure partnership interaction with the global educational community.

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